

Dossier de evidencias – CONFIA 2018

Combined 2D animation in television series

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Actas (URL estable)

Conferencia: CONFIA – 6th International Conference on Illustration and Animation

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5. Enlaces y códigos QR

Ficha técnica / Technical sheet

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Enlaces / Links

Actas (URL estable):

https://confia.ipca.pt/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/confia_2018_proceedings.pdf

DOI Zenodo (depósito):

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18833367>

17:00 PANEL 14 :: MODERATION LINDA SCOTT :: ENGLISH

JOÃO FIGUEIREDO

Time, Movement and Narrative - Relations between Comic and Picturebooks

DULCE MELÃO

To hear with eyes belongs to love's fine wit»: illustration as a «nurturing» gesture in picturebooks

KAROLINA KORNEK FREIXIAL

Authors' silent picturebooks for children and adults, from outside the English-speaking culture. An introduction to the research

17:45 COFFEE BREAK

17:45 PANEL 15 :: MODERATION JORGE TEIXEIRA MARQUES :: ENGLISH

ANA LOPES

Approaches to authorship in video games: the director, the studio and the players

SÓNIA RAFAEL

Interactive Fiction. Narrative and immersive experience in text-based games.

GABRIELA SÁ

Desperfeitamente - an activity book for inducing creativity in female character design

18:30 SPECIAL PANEL

Expanded Image Spaces: Animation as an Artistic Practice

Meaning and Temporality in Abstract Animation
Max Hattler

On Film between Painting and Sculpture
Robert Seidel

Site-Specific Sand Animation for Jewish Museum
Pedro Serrazina

21:00 OFICIAL CONFERENCE DINNER /// SUAVE MAR HOTEL

CONFERENCE PROGRAMME 15 JULY /// SUNDAY

10:15 PANEL 16 :: MODERATION PEDRO MOTA TEIXEIRA :: ENGLISH

CONCHA GARCÍA

Metamorphoses (a project on the multiple identities that inhabit us)

SARA COVELO

Collaborative Construction of an Androgynous Character for a Short Animated Film: Dani

SARA COSTA

Gosma: a project with a trans-media approach

11:00 COFFEE BREAK

11:15 PANEL 17 :: MODERATION MANUEL ALBINO :: PORTUGUÊS

CIDÁLIA MARQUES

Painéis Murais "Edutainment" - o Parque das Termas da Curia

FERNANDO CORREIA

O Delta Jurássico da Lourinhã - a "Paleoarte" como Veículo para ir mais além do Tempo

SARA MATOS

Imaginário infantil como base do processo de ilustração do conto "O Elefante Apaixonado"

12:00 PANEL 18 :: MODERATION PEDRO SARMENTO :: PORTUGUÊS

NAJLA LEROY

O contributo dos recursos narrativos no contexto da expansão da audiência do álbum ilustrado contemporâneo

CIBELE SAQUE

Uma Linha Que Desenha Olhar

DIANA MARIA MARTINS

Contributos para a História do livro-objecto/brinquedo em Portugal: alguns volumes de fazer Oh! creativity in female character design

MARCIO GODOY

"A luz é como a água": uma aventura pelo movimento

CONFERENCE PROGRAMME

13 JULY /// FRIDAY

wi-fi network Auditorio

password esposende

09:00 WELCOME DESK /// REGISTRATION

09:30 MUSICAL OPENING

09:45 OPENING SPEECH

Angélica Cruz Esposende city counciler for education

Patrícia Gomes IPCA's vice-president

Paula Tavares Confia's general chair

10:00 KEYNOTE

Hannes Rall New Beginnings and Continued Traditions: Redefining Animated Storytelling for New Technologies?

11:00 COFFEE BREAK

11:15 PANEL 1 :: MODERATION HANNES RALL :: ENGLISH

FILIPA CRUZ

The magical unfathomable of Animation: The unknown, the unseen and the folklore

SERGIO RODRIGUEZ

Combined 2D animation in television series

ALEX JUKES

Specificity of Digital Media: The Medium of 3-D CGI and Other Media

12:00 PANEL 2 :: MODERATION ALAN MALE :: ENGLISH

JUDIT FERENCZ

The Graphic Novel as a New Interdisciplinary Conservation Method in Architectural Heritage: A Book of Hours for Robin Hood Gardens

DAVE WOOD

What Do You See? Using the Graphic Novella to Challenge Stigma

SANDRA CARDOSO

The pact between words and images: Big Words, an illustrated book

12:45 CONFERENCE LUNCH

15:15 PANEL 3 :: MODERATION JÚLIO DOLBETH :: ENGLISH

VINCENT LARKIN

Shifting Identities within Internet Memes

ANA SABINO

Thinking through drawing

LINDA SCOTT

Innocence Lost And The Landscapes Of Darkness: Shedding Light On Embedded Political Themes In Illustrated Narratives

participation certificate

We hereby certify that **Sergio Rodriguez Valdunciel** was a speaker at CONFIA 2018 - 6th International Illustration and Animation Conference, in Esposende, Portugal, organized by Escola Superior de Design at IPCA - Instituto Politécnico do Cávado e Ave and presented the paper **Combined 2D animation in television series**.

Esposende, 16th July 2018

PAULA TAVARES
GENERAL CHAIR

**CON
FIA**
2018

**INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE ON
ILLUSTRATION
& ANIMATION**
13 > 15 JULY
ESPOSENDE | PORTUGAL

SPEAKER

